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TECHNOLOGIZED INFORMATION SPACE OF MODERN SOCIETY

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ТЕХНОЛОГИЗИРОВАННОЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЕ ПРОСТРАНСТВО СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБЩЕСТВА

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ZAMONAVIY JAMIYATNING TEXNOLOGLASHTIRILGAN AXBOROT MAKONI

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abstract

This article discusses the culture of intelligence, the technological information space of modern society, the formation of human intellectual culture, the basic fundamental features of man, post-industrial society, intellectual elite, social strata.

asosiy fundamental xususiyatlari, postindustrial jamiyat, intellektual elita, ijtimoiy qatlamlar muhokama qilinadi.

Keywords:

postindustrial society, intellectual elite, social strata, technology, information space, Noosphere.

аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются культура интеллекта, технологическое информационное пространство современного общества, формирование интеллектуальной культуры человека, основные фундаментальные черты человека, постиндустриальное общество, интеллектуальная элита, социальные слои.

Ключевые слова:

постиндустриальное общество, интеллектуальная элита, социальные слои, технологии, информационное поле, Ноосфера.

annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada aql madaniyati, zamonaviy jamiyatning texnologik axborot makoni, inson intellektual madaniyatining shakllanishi, insonning

Kalit so'zlar:

postindustrial jamiyat, intellektual elita, ijtimoiy qatlamlar, texnologiya, axborot maydoni, noosfera.

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Introduction

The intellectual culture of a person is largely determined by his independent opinion, work activity and way of living. Therefore, the culture of intelligibility of a person is associated not only with his physical and spiritual qualities, but also with his lifestyle, material well-being. Through its culture of intelligibility, a person increasingly discovers himself deeper and more clearly, based on the extent to which

he reflects reality and deepens his thoughts about it. That is, the “culture of intelligence” of a person will be focused primarily on the realization of his self. The spiritual-moral maturity of a person is largely determined by the level of intellectual culture. This process is related to the theoretical knowledge and practical experiences that arise from the daily and scientific level that a person accumulates during his quest for self-knowledge. Also in this process, the level of intellectual culture of each person is distinguished by its significant features. Because with the fact that the profession, specialty, degree of specialization and lifestyle of some people are close to each other, the culture of their intelligibility is manifested to varying degrees.

Research results

The technologized information space of modern society has a number of distinctive features that affect the formation of human intellectual culture:

- the emergence of an intellectual class, whose representatives at the political level participate as consultants, experts or technocrats;
- strengthening the position of theoretical knowledge with the status of a strategic resource;
- creation of a space of the intellectual environment on the basis of a computer; strengthening the basic fundamental characteristics of a person, for example, the production of intelligence, activity, the desire for creativity and freedom;
- the emergence of the intellectual elite, the formation of new spiritual and moral qualities of a person: mobility, high professionalism, the ability to change activities and the possibility of acquiring new professions;
- the change of human nature in the direction of the “noosphere” ;
- the emergence of new forms of collective consciousness means the study and unification of people.[1]

The emergence of a class of intellectuals, highly qualified specialists, manufacturers of high - quality products lead to the emergence of a new phenomenon- an elite culture that concentrates the spiritual, intellectual and artistic experiences of generations.

Postindustrial society concept author D.As Bell notes, “post-industrial society is characterized by a new elite based on qualifications acquired as a result of education, rather than on property inherited or acquired through entrepreneurial abilities”. Representatives of the intellectual elite are distinguished by the following qualities:

- high intellectual abilities; high level of quality education;
- the breadth and versatility of worldview forms (as opposed to industrial-era specialization;

- ability and willingness to learn throughout life with the aim of creating new knowledge;
- mobility, including vertical, is not based on gender and age, but on personal ability;
- it is independence from attachment to the workplace.[2]

E. Toffler uses the concept of "knowing", which he introduced into scientific treatment with similar scientific characteristics, instead of the concept of "intellectual elite".[3] Some researchers, including M.G. In addition to the class of intellectuals (cognitarists) who are the creators of information and intellectual product, Bresler also distinguishes the upper layer of society - the owners of intellectual, information products and information and communication networks.[4] also, some scholars consider the lower tier of society - information and intellectual products interpret their consumers separately. With this approach, a strict hierarchical social structure is formed with a vertical line of influence on the higher-level perception community and the lower class. Because the creators of an intellectual product, firstly, practically do not distribute the system of consumer values introduced by the upper class, and secondly, on the basis of personal choice, they may or may not pass on their results. The proposed strict hierarchical social structure is typical of the industrial era, and in practice does not reflect the peculiarities of the Information Society, which tend to destroy all rigid structures, paving the way for another network structure, which is more suitable for the intellectual and information space of society. The creation of the space of the intellectual environment makes it possible to implement the sectoral principle of the organization of mental labor.

The dramatic changes, updates, great inventions, the result of which is the product of human consciousness, which are taking place in the current era of human development, are setting tasks that are qualitatively new and relatively complex. Of particular importance in this is the level of development of the culture of intelligibility in people, the regulator of its mental capabilities, spiritual and moral aspects. To date, the complex study and analysis of scientific literature shows that this problem has been studied quite extensively since the beginning of the 20th century.

The intellectual culture of a person is largely determined by his independent opinion, work activity and way of living. Therefore, the culture of intelligibility of a person is associated not only with his physical and spiritual qualities, but also with his lifestyle, material well-being. Through its culture of intelligibility, a person increasingly discovers himself deeper and more clearly, based on the extent to which he reflects reality and deepens his thoughts about it. That is, the "culture of intelligence" of a person will be focused primarily on the realization of his self. The

spiritual-moral maturity of a person is largely determined by the level of intellectual culture. This process is related to the theoretical knowledge and practical experiences that arise from the daily and scientific level that a person accumulates during his quest for self-knowledge. Also in this process, the level of intellectual culture of each person is distinguished by its significant features. Because with the fact that the profession, specialty, degree of specialization and lifestyle of some people are close to each other, the culture of their intelligibility is manifested to varying degrees. The history of human civilization is evidenced by the fact that society at all times has highly Embodied Intelligence, felt the need for great talents and abilities. As an ideal of society, people of the highest example and their sermazmun activities have always been of socio-educational importance. This is due to the fact that during a long period in the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan, education and cultural values have been carefully maintained, respected, constantly protected and multiplied as a high spiritual factor in the education of intellectual people and are being brought up.

Conclusion

Our homeland is following the path of building a legal democratic state and civil society. The years since the independence of our country have been a period of tremendous testing and renewal for our people and our young state. During this period, in conjunction with the revival of our national values, great attention was paid to further elevating the culture of the intelligentsia of the future generation, as well as educating the harmonious generation with the progressive ideas of modern science. Therefore, as a result of the clash of ideas, which is a derivative of the scientific and technological revolution of today, the sharp negative consequences of various changes in the thinking of our people, that is, various ideological threats and protection from the resulting inertia and marginalism of thinking, as well as the development of important methods and means of alternative elevation of the intellectual culture of

The most important thing is that in the implementation of these tasks we define our attitude to our existing scientific potential, as well as to the various views that exist in our past and today, one of the most subtle and necessary aspects of enhancing the spiritual potential of our ring. It is absolutely impossible to develop an alternative culture of personality and society in the country without objectively analyzing and researching these aspects. Somehow, the approach to the problem of elevating the culture of intelligibility from an objective point of view, the research of the laws of its development, the personality and society are one of the most basic tasks in the formation of the culture of intelligibility. This, in turn, is important in the education of the younger generation of adults, as well as specialists-personnel as a perfect person.

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